

1 **Detection of unrecorded environmental challenges in high**
2 **frequency recorded traits, and genetic determinism of**
3 **resilience to challenge, with an application in feed intake of**
4 **lambs**

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21 **Abstract**

22
23 **Background:** Resilient animals are capable of remaining productive under different
24 environmental conditions. Rearing in increasingly heterogeneous environmental conditions
25 increases the need of selecting resilient animals. Detection of environmental challenges
26 affecting the entire population can provide a unique opportunity to select animals more resilient
27 to those events. The objective of this study was two-fold. First, to present a simple and practical
28 data-driven approach to estimate the probability that at a given date there was an unrecorded
29 environmental challenge occurring. Second, to evaluate genetic determinism of resilience to
30 these events.

31 **Methods:** Here we present a method that consists in, first, inferring the existence of highly
32 variable days (indicator of environmental challenge) *via* mixture models applied to frequent
33 phenotypic records and second, using the inferred probabilities of occurrence of an
34 environmental challenge in a reaction norm model to evaluate genetic determinism of resilience
35 to these events. These probabilities are estimated for each day (or other time frame). We
36 illustrated the method using an ovine dataset with daily feed intake (DFI) records.

37 **Results:** We were able to estimate probabilities of occurrence of an unrecorded environmental
38 challenge using the proposed method. These probabilities proved to be informative and useful
39 to include as a covariate in a reaction norm animal model. We estimated breeding values for
40 environmental sensitivity of the genetic potential for DFI of the animals. The level and slope
41 showed to be negatively correlated (-0.46 ± 0.21).

42 **Conclusions:** The method is promising and seems viable to identify unrecorded environmental
43 challenges events, useful when selecting resilient animals and only productive data are
44 available. It is generalizable to a wide variety of phenotypic records from different species and
45 useful when dealing with large quantities of data. The negative correlation between the level

46 and slope, shows that a hypothetical selection for increased or decreased DFI would result in
47 increased susceptibility to stress for this trait. A reranking of individual was observed along the
48 environmental gradient as well as low genetic correlations among extreme environmental
49 conditions. These confirmed the existence of GxE interaction, showing that the best animals in
50 one environmental condition are not the best in another one.

51

52 **Key words:** environmental challenge, mixture models, reaction norm animal model,
53 resilience.

54

55 **Background**

56 Resilience (also referred to as robustness) is the capacity of an animal to be minimally affected
57 by disturbances or to rapidly return to the state pertained before exposure to a disturbance or
58 environmental challenge [1,2]. Traditionally the focus of livestock breeding goals has been on
59 traits directly related to production performance. Actually, the increasingly wide variety of
60 environmental conditions in which livestock is required to perform is rapidly moving attention
61 to robustness traits [3]. Rearing in increasingly heterogeneous environmental conditions
62 increases the need of selecting resilient animals. In these conditions, animals can be exposed to
63 different types of challenges or disturbances such as nutritional availability, thermal stress,
64 disease pressure, etc. [4]. Under real productive rearing conditions, challenge events are
65 sometimes unrecorded and from unknown source, and traditionally there were not frequent
66 enough data to be able to quantify resilience, given that it involves dynamic processes that are
67 difficult to follow with few records as discussed by Friggens et al. [4].

68 Repeated measurements over time have a high potential for quantification of the animal's
69 ability to cope with environmental challenges [4]. Nowadays high frequent data is becoming
70 increasingly available due to high frequency recording systems such as automated monitoring
71 technology or robot milking. The availability of a large volume of data enables to follow the
72 whole process in which the response to and recovery from perturbations of an animal occurs
73 [4] but it also sets a challenge that involves dealing with a high amount of records. In general,
74 the information recorded is related to productive performance (e.g. weights, milk production,
75 feed intake, etc.) but comparatively little information (if any) is available related to variables
76 that can help identifying environmental challenges such as climatic factors, problems related to
77 health (e.g. pathogen load), etc. However, their effect on animal performance can be observed
78 indirectly, through changes (variability patterns) in repeated records of performance over time
79 as shown by Nguyen-Ba et al. [5] for voluntary feed intake in pigs. In small ruminants, Colditz

80 and Hine [1] and Friggens et al. [6] reported significant variation between animals in their
81 response profiles to thermal and nutritional challenges, respectively. Variation increased related
82 to the occurrence of and environmental challenge.

83 Some approaches have been proposed to identify variation in high frequency data sets related
84 to the occurrence of environmental challenges. For example, Codrea et al. [7] presented a
85 smoothing approach to detect production deviations related to disturbances in the time series of
86 milk production. Berghof et al. [8] proposed resilience indicators based on standardized body
87 weight (BW) deviations in layer chicken. Nguyen-Ba et al. [5] proposed a procedure to detect
88 the impact of perturbations in growing pigs and quantify the feed intake response in terms of
89 resistance and resilience. This method involves the estimation of a target trajectory of
90 cumulative feed intake and, then detecting deviations from this target curve. In all these studies,
91 challenges were artificially introduced and consequently, known and recorded. On the other
92 hand, Poppe et al. [9] proposed three indicators based on fluctuation patterns in milk yield
93 related to unknown disturbances. For the three of them, it is necessary to estimate a lactation
94 curve for each animal as a first step. All these studies show that there is increased variability
95 related to environmental challenges but there is not a single method to detect perturbations in
96 rearing conditions in which only records of the traits of interest are available but there is very
97 little (if any) information related to environmental conditions.

98
99 Detection of environmental challenges affecting the entire population (herd, flock or farm) can
100 provide a unique opportunity to select animals more resilient to those events, as all individuals
101 are exposed to the same environmental conditions. A simple indicator of environmental
102 challenge is increased phenotypic variation due to different responses of individuals to stress.
103 It is of interest, thus, to determine if this is a valid indicator of stress and if the response to this
104 possible stress is genetically determined.

105 The objective of this study was two-fold: 1) to present a simple and practical data-driven
106 approach to estimate the probability that at a given date there was an unrecorded environmental
107 challenge occurring, using a mixture model of phenotypic variances, and 2) to evaluate genetic
108 determinism of resilience to these events, using these probabilities as covariates in a reaction
109 norm model. In this study, we analyzed an ovine dataset but it is important to notice that the
110 methods are very general and can be employed in other species and traits.

111

112

113 **Methods**

114

115 *Finite mixture models and estimation of the probability of occurrence of an unrecorded* 116 *environmental challenge for each day*

117

118 According to McLachlan and Peel [10], in practice there are some cases where the population is
119 a mixture of n distinct groups that are known *a priori* to exist in some physical sense. Finite
120 mixture models are applicable where there is group-structure in the data [11]. For instance, a
121 source of heterogeneity can be age, sex, a disease (presence or absence), etc. [10]. In the same
122 logic, we hypothesized that environmental challenges produce different reactions in the
123 animals, leading to larger phenotypic variance as shown in previous studies (e.g. [1,5,6]). In
124 fact, Scheffer et al. [12] refers to the variance as a “dynamic indicator of resilience”, as it can
125 be useful to monitor dynamically changes in a system. Thus, we expect a data set to contain a
126 (at least) two-component normal mixture model: one for “normal” days, and another for
127 “stressful” days with high variability related to the occurrence of an environmental challenge.
128 The number of components is, though, unclear and should be inferred from the data.

129 Following Chen et al. [13], the trait values related to the presence or absence of a disturbance
130 are distributed as $N(\mu_1, \sigma_1^2)$ and $N(\mu_2, \sigma_2^2)$, respectively. Then the population quantitative trait
131 under study has a two-component normal mixture distribution

$$132 \quad \text{Var}(y) = \sum_{i=1}^2 \alpha_i N(\mu_i, \sigma_i^2)$$

133 where α_i are the mixing proportions (nonnegative and summing to one) and $N(\mu_i, \sigma_i^2)$ are the
134 component densities.

135 There are different approaches to estimate mixture distributions. The most commonly used is
136 the fitting of mixture models by maximum likelihood estimation via the estimation-
137 maximization (EM) algorithm of Dempster et al. [14], [10]. Distribution component parameters,
138 mixing proportions and posterior component membership probabilities are estimated. These are
139 probabilities that a given day belongs to the first or second component of the mixture. These
140 probabilities can be used with two different purposes, either for clustering (“normal” or
141 “stressful” days) or directly as an environmental descriptor continuous variable to characterize
142 the environmental gradient. A problem in clustering is the choice of an arbitrary cut-off, with
143 loss of information in particular if the two components of the mixture overlap. The mixture
144 model needs data, so it is expected to be accurate with frequent records (e.g. daily) but not with
145 sporadic ones (e.g. monthly). Preliminary tests with monthly milk recordings in dairy sheep
146 could not show the existence of more than one component in the mixture (results not shown).
147 Moreover, the method requires homogeneity of animals within groups, to avoid variability
148 given by difference in age for example. In that case, lambs and adults should be analyzed
149 separately.

150 So, our method is as follows:

- 151 1. Fit a mixture model to raw data. On output, there may be two (or more)
152 components. The component with larger variance is associated to stress or
153 challenge.
- 154 2. Include the probability of belonging to “stressful” component as a covariate in a
155 reaction norm animal model.

156 This approach is simple and practical as it enables to analyze all the phenotypic data together
157 from all individuals, and to estimate the probability that at a given date there was an unrecorded
158 environmental challenge occurring based on the variability observed for each day. There is no
159 need of an initial step to estimate, first, an observed or a target curve (e.g. a growth or milk
160 yield curve), with all the parameters that this implies, and, second, the deviations from the curve
161 as indicators of environmental challenges. Thus, instead of measuring deviations within
162 individuals across time we measure deviations across individuals within time. Moreover, this
163 approach can be employed for different datasets coming from different species and with records
164 from different kind of traits, as it only focuses on daily (or other time frame) variability.

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166

167 *Animals and phenotypes*

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169 The present study was carried out in agreement with the French National Regulations for
170 humane care and use of animals for research purposes (Décret 2013/118). Animals were bred
171 at the experimental INRAE Farm (La Sapinière, Osmoy, France) which has the experimental
172 approval C18-174-01.

173 Data is fully described in [15,16]. Here we summarize the main aspects. Data for the analysis
174 were from Romane male lambs evaluated as part of the national Romane breeding scheme.
175 Every year, over an 8-year period (from 2009 to 2016), a cohort of Romane male lambs were
176 continuously phenotyped during 8 weeks for feeding behavior, totalizing 951 lambs. On

177 average, each year 119 lambs were tested varying from 92 to 149 animals per year. Each year,
178 after weaning, all the lambs of approximately the same age (70 days on average, ranging from
179 60 to 90 days) were grouped in 5 to 8 pens with a mean of 20 animals each (ranging from 13 to
180 27). Each pen had an automatic concentrate feeder (ACF). A 14-day period of adaptation to the
181 new environment was necessary, followed by an 8-week period in which the animals were
182 tested during winter.

183 Lambs were fed low-energy concentrated pellets *ad libitum*. Feed intake was continuously
184 recorded during a period of 8 weeks each year during winter. Every time (from now on called
185 “a visit”) the animal was identified by the ACF, the quantity of concentrate consumed and the
186 duration of the visit were recorded. For more details regarding the low-energy concentrated diet
187 and the functioning of the ACF refer to [15,16].

188 A total of 775,580 visit records were available for all eight periods, with an average of 14.56
189 visits per day per animal. All visit records within each day were summed up to obtain the daily
190 feed intake (DFI). A total of 51,832 DFI records were available for all animals over the eight
191 years. As the data were recorded in growing animals, the tendency for DFI (and its variance as
192 well, due to a scale effect) is to increase as the animal gets bigger over time. In order to take
193 this into account, we employed the (natural logarithm of) daily Coefficient of Variation (CV)
194 instead of the daily variance to assess variability. This represents a total of 438 days across the
195 8 years, 55 days per year on average approximately. For the further genetic analysis, a total of
196 5,114 animals were included in the pedigree constituted of the 951 tested lambs and their
197 ancestors.

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199 ***Fitting a finite mixture model and estimating probabilities of occurrence of an unrecorded***
200 ***environmental challenge in a Romane lamb population***

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203 We used the *normalmixEM* function in the R library *mixtools* [17] to implement the Gaussian
204 mixture model to the data consisting of 438 values of $\log(\text{CV})$ registered for each day during
205 the 8 years. The mixture fitting procedure involves the estimation-maximization (EM)
206 algorithm [10]. Both the mean and the variance of both components were initially
207 unconstrained. Even though we had some *a priori* information to fit a mixture of two
208 components, we used a parametric bootstrap to confirm the number of components. This
209 procedure tests sequentially the null hypothesis of a k -component mixture Gaussian distribution
210 [10,17]. In this way, we were able to confirm that a mixture of two normal components was
211 appropriate to model the data.

212 We also computed posterior probabilities for each day (within each year) of pertaining to the
213 first or the second component of the mixture distribution. Days with high probability of
214 pertaining to the first component were “low CV days”, while those with high probability of
215 pertaining to the second component were “high CV days”. Those days with high probability of
216 having a high CV, showed increased variability, probably related to the occurrence of an
217 environmental challenge. Probabilities of pertaining to the second component were taken as a
218 reference and employed in the genetic analysis described below. In summary, these
219 probabilities quantify the possibility that at a given date there was an unrecorded environmental
220 challenge occurring.

221 These probabilities can be employed directly (as a continuous variable) within a genetic model
222 to describe the environment without the need to assign each of the days to a discrete
223 (categorical) variable. These probabilities permit to describe the environment through a gradient
224 going from a non-challenging environment ($p = 0$) to a challenging one ($p = 1$) and the intensity

225 of the challenge can be quantified through the probability. Moreover, each individual has one
 226 record of DFI per day and one probability p per day, and these probabilities vary across the
 227 days. For these two reasons, it is convenient to employ a reaction norm model including these
 228 probabilities as an environmental descriptor as presented below.

229 De Jong [18] defined the reaction norm as the total pattern of expression of a character along a
 230 continuous gradient given by an environmental descriptor. Calus and Veerkamp [19] discuss
 231 that environmental descriptors should i) reflect management and environment, ii) be obtained
 232 from available data and iii) be continuous rather than categorical. The estimated probabilities
 233 that at a given date there was an unrecorded environmental challenge meet these conditions.

234

235

236 *Genetic Analysis*

237

238 Phenotypes (DFI) were analyzed using a linear Reaction Norm Animal Model (RNAM)
 239 including the estimated probabilities that at a given date there was an unrecorded environmental
 240 challenge occurring, to evaluate genetic determinism of resilience to unrecorded environmental
 241 challenges. The model employed was:

$$242 \quad y_{ijk} = \text{yearACF}_i + b_1 \text{day}_j + a_{0,k} + a_{1,k} * p_j + pe_{0,k} + pe_{1,k} * p_j + e_{ijk}$$

243

244 Where y_{ijk} is the observation of DFI (in kg) in yearACF i , day j for animal k . Preliminary
 245 analyses were performed by Marie-Etancelin et al. [16] and Tortereau et al. [15] to determine
 246 the fixed effects to take into account in the genetic analyses. Only two fixed effects were
 247 significant: year (eight levels) and ACF device (up to seven levels per year). These were
 248 combined into one term (yearACF_i , $i = 1$ to 44) in the model. The second term corresponds to
 249 a regression on the day j to take into account the effect of growing over DFI; $a_{0,k}$ is the breeding
 250 value (BV) for level (or intercept) of DFI and corresponds to the classical BV for performance

251 potential for animal k (it is environment-independent); $a_{1,k}$ is the BV for slope (environmental
 252 sensitivity) of DFI for animal k , p_j is the probability that at day j there was an unrecorded
 253 environmental challenges occurring; $pe_{0,k}$ is the permanent environmental effect of animal k
 254 (intercept), $pe_{1,k}$ is the permanent environmental effect of animal k for p_j (slope) and e_{ijk} is the
 255 residual. A slope of $a_{1,k} = 0$ means that the animal is not sensitive to stress; a slope of $a_{1,k} <$
 256 0 means that the animal takes less food in stressful environments; a slope of $a_{1,k} > 0$ means
 257 that it takes more.

258 The two traits a_0 and a_1 are assumed to follow a bivariate distribution with $Var \begin{pmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \end{pmatrix} =$
 259 $\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{a_0}^2 & \sigma_{a_0,a_1} \\ \sigma_{a_0,a_1} & \sigma_{a_1}^2 \end{pmatrix}$. On the other hand, pe_0 and pe_1 are assumed to follow a bivariate distribution
 260 with $Var \begin{pmatrix} pe_0 \\ pe_1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{pe_0}^2 & \sigma_{pe_0,pe_1} \\ \sigma_{pe_0,pe_1} & \sigma_{pe_1}^2 \end{pmatrix}$.

261 For comparison, another Animal Model (AM) was fitted without the reaction norm terms, i.e.
 262 without $a_{1,k} * p_j$ and $pe_{1,k} * p_j$.

263

264 ***Variance component estimation and model comparison***

265 (Co)variance components were estimated using Gibbs sampling and REML using the software
 266 GIBBSF90 and AIREMLF90, (available at <http://nce.ads.uga.edu/wiki/>) respectively [20]. For
 267 the Gibbs sampling, a total of 200,000 iterations were run, with burn-in of 10,000 initial
 268 iterations and sample interval of 10. Posterior means and posterior standard deviations (SD)
 269 were calculated. For REML, the asymptotic standard error for the genetic correlation was
 270 computed following Houle and Meyer [21], as implemented in AIREMLF90. For this purpose,
 271 we run first EM-REML for all the initial iterations and then switched to AI in the final iteration.
 272 This was done because EM-REML algorithm is much more stable than the AI algorithm and

273 very robust to poor initial estimates so it can provide a good starting point for the AI algorithm
 274 [22].

275 A likelihood ratio test was performed from REML results to assess goodness of fit and to
 276 compare the RNAM and the traditional AM. The χ^2 were calculated as $\chi^2 = -2\log L_{AM} +$
 277 $2\log L_{RNAM}$, the first term is the AM likelihood and the second is the RNAM likelihood. *P*-
 278 values of the Chi-squared tests were obtained from a mixture of Chi-squared distributions with
 279 2 and 4 degrees of freedom [23,24].

280 For a given level of covariate *p*, total genetic variance is $\sigma_{a0}^2 + 2\sigma_{a0,a1} + p^2\sigma_{a1}^2$, similarly for
 281 variance due to permanent environment, and from here it is possible to obtain values of
 282 heritability that change across conditions (i.e. from *p* = 0 to *p* = 1).

283 The genetic correlation between the breeding value in a non-challenging environment (*p* = 0)
 284 and the breeding value at a given probability of occurrence of an environmental challenge (*p*)
 285 was calculated as

$$286 \quad Cor(a_0, a_p) = \frac{Cov(a_0, a_p)}{\sqrt{Var(a_0)Var(a_p)}} = \frac{\sigma_{a0}^2 + \sigma_{a0,a1} * p}{\sqrt{\sigma_{a0}^2(\sigma_{a0}^2 + p^2\sigma_{a1}^2 + 2p\sigma_{a0,a1})}}$$

287

288 Results

289

290 *Fitting a finite mixture model and estimating probabilities of occurrence of an unrecorded* 291 *environmental challenge in a Romane lamb population*

292

293 The histogram in Figure 1 shows, on the right side, a subgroup of observations that seemed to

294 have values of the natural logarithm of the CV of DFI higher than the majority of the records

295 on the left (higher than -1.4). This was an initial hint that there could be two different groups of

296 days considering the variability of the DFI records. This was confirmed once a two-component

297 normal mixture model was fitted. Figure 1 also shows the density of two-component normal

298 mixture fitted on the $\log(\text{CV})$ of DFI. The two components fitted are heteroscedastic and have

299 different means. The first component (red in the figure) has a mean of -1.60 and a SD 0.13, and

300 the second component (green in the figure), a mean of -1.42 and a SD 0.27.

301

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303

304 **Figure 1.** Plot of the log-transformed CV of DFI data of the fitted two component (red and
305 green) normal mixture model.
306

307 The EM algorithm for mixtures allows to estimate the probability that each day belongs to the
308 environmental challenge class of the mixture. These probabilities are shown in Figure 2. The
309 mean of these probabilities was 0.09, showing that most of the days the probability of
310 occurrence of an environmental challenge was low. In this figure some years (2, 3, 7) had days
311 with a probability higher than 0.90 of occurrence of an environmental challenge. Furthermore,
312 only a 3.88 % of the days across different years were found to have probabilities higher than
313 0.5 of being a challenge day. Most days showed a probability lower than 0.25.

314 We carried out a posterior analysis focused on those days with high estimated probability p of
315 occurrence of an environmental challenge. The aim was to check if these days corresponded to
316 known disturbances in the experimental farm. We confirmed that some of the days with high
317 value of p (high probability of being stressful) were associated to changes in management
318 weighting of the animals, mulching, or fixing (repairing) some ACF. However, there was no
319 other explanation for other days with high p and we assume that these are unrecorded
320 environmental challenges.

321

322

323 **Figure 2.** Probabilities of showing a high CV (related to the occurrence of an environmental challenge) for each of the days. These values
 324 correspond to the probability of pertaining to the second component of the mixture of the two Gaussian distributions.

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327

328 ***Genetic Analysis***

329

330 Table 1 shows the variance components estimates for DFI using the RNAM and AM model.

331 The genetic correlation between the level and sensitivity to inferred environmental challenge

332 was -0.46 ± 0.21 , showing that level is antagonistic to environmental sensitivity. A hypothetical

333 selection for increased DFI under no stressful conditions (which is generally the case) would

334 result in animals with decreased DFI in stressful conditions. If, on the contrary, selection is

335 made for decreased DFI it would result in animals with increased DFI in stressful conditions.

336

337 **Table 1.** Parameter estimates obtained using the animal model (AM) and the reaction norm
 338 animal model (RNAM).

Parameter	Model	
	AM	RNAM
σ_{a0}^2	0.014	0.016
σ_{a1}^2	-	0.038
$\sigma_{a0,a1}$	-	-0.011
σ_{pe0}^2	0.028	0.034
σ_{pe1}^2	-	0.104
$\sigma_{pe0,pe1}$	-	-0.031
σ_e^2	0.123	0.120
Genetic correlation	-	-0.46 ± 0.21

339 σ_{a0}^2 = additive genetic variance for level , σ_{a1}^2 = additive genetic variance for slope, $\sigma_{a0,a1}$ =
 340 additive genetic covariance between level and slope, σ_{pe0}^2 = permanent environmental variance
 341 for level, σ_{pe1}^2 = permanent environmental variance for slope, $\sigma_{pe0,pe1}$ = permanent
 342 environmental covariance between level and slope, σ_e^2 = residual variance.

343
 344 Goodness of fit of the models was assessed by performing a likelihood ratio test (Table 2).
 345 Model RNAM fitted the data much better than AM. This shows that the log(CV) is a valid
 346 indicator for the genetic analysis and may be of value to select for resilience.

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348

349 **Table 2.** Goodness of fit, likelihood ratio test of models AM and RNAM.

-2 log likelihood		Likelihood ratio test	
AM	RNAM	χ^2	P-value
41219.52	40685.54	533.98	$1.50 \cdot 10^{-114}$

350

355 **Figure 3.** Heritability estimates for DFI for different probabilities of occurrence of an
 356 environmental challenge (p is the environmental descriptor in which zero indicates non-
 357 challenging environmental conditions and, conversely, one indicates highly challenging
 358 conditions).

359

360 Figure 3 shows the heritability estimates for DFI for different probabilities of occurrence of an
361 environmental challenge. The values ranged from 0.08 (for $p = 0.30$) to 0.14 (for $p = 1$).
362 Heritability for DFI decreased going from $p = 0$ to $p = 0.30$ and later increased for higher values
363 of p . These behavior was comparable to that reported by Ravagnolo and Misztal [25] and
364 Kolmodin et al. [26] in dairy cattle. In both studies genetic parameters changed over different
365 environments. Marie-Etancelin et al. [16] reported a higher value of heritability for average DFI
366 for the same ovine population analyzed in this study. Heritability of DFI is lower than that of
367 average DFI because the latter contains less noise, as it is averaged over time.

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371

$(p \approx 0)$
Non – challenging
environmental conditions

$(p \approx 1)$
Challenging environmental
conditions

372 **Figure 4.** Level (a_0), environmental sensitivity (a_1) and total additive (a_0+a_1) variances for DFI
 373 for different probabilities of occurrence of an environmental challenge (p is the environmental
 374 descriptor in which zero indicates non-challenging environmental conditions and, conversely,
 375 one indicates highly challenging conditions).

376

377 Figure 4 shows the estimates of level (a_0), environmental sensitivity (a_1) and total additive
 378 ($a_0 + p \times a_1$) variances for DFI for increasing probabilities of occurrence of an environmental
 379 challenge (going from non-challenging environmental conditions to more challenging ones).
 380 Under non-challenging environmental conditions ($p = 0$), the additive variance for
 381 environmental sensitivity is 0 and starts to increase for higher values of p (more challenging

382 environmental conditions), reaching its maximum value (0.04 kg^2) when $p = 1$. As there is a
 383 negative covariance between level and slope, the total additive variance first decreases slightly
 384 as p increases and later, for higher values of p , it starts to increase.

385

386 $(p \approx 0)$ $(p \approx 1)$

387 Non – challenging Challenging environmental

388 environmental conditions conditions

389

390 **Figure 5.** Genetic correlation between breeding values in a non-challenging environment ($p =$
 391 0) and breeding value at a given probability of occurrence of an environmental challenge (p).

392

393 Figure 5 shows the genetic correlation between EBV in a non-challenging environment ($p = 0$)
 394 and breeding value at a given probability of occurrence of an environmental challenge (p). For
 395 low values of p (going from 0 to 0.15 - non-challenging environmental conditions) the

396 correlation is close to one (from 0.97 to 1). For values higher than 0.15 of p , the correlation
397 starts to decrease and reaches its minimum value (0.21) for $p = 1$. Low genetic correlations
398 among challenging and non-challenging environments indicate reranking of individuals in
399 different environmental conditions. It also implies that selection under completely non-
400 challenging conditions is ineffective for expression of the trait in completely challenging
401 conditions.

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406 **Figure 6. a.** Change in EBV between a non-challenging environmental condition ($p = 0$) and an extremely challenging one ($p = 1$) expressed in terms of genetic
407 standard deviation. Three groups were identified according to the pattern of reaction to environmental challenging conditions and are shown with different
408 colors in the histogram (red: those animals whose EBVs decrease for higher values of p ; blue: those animals whose EBVs tend to remain approximately
409 constant for higher values of p , within -1 and +1 genetic standard deviations; green: those animals whose EBVs increase for higher values of p). A total of 20
410 animals were randomly sampled from each group and **b, c, d** show the reaction norms for DFI for each of the three groups.

411

412 Figure 6 shows the change in EBV between non-challenge ($p = 0$) and challenge ($p = 1$)
413 expressed in terms of genetic standard deviation. Three groups of animals were identified
414 according to the pattern of change. The majority of the individuals (98.20 %) were within the
415 second group (in blue in Figure 6), 1.13% of the individuals were within the first group (in red
416 in Figure 6) and 0.67% were within the third group (in green in Figure 6). As it can be seen in
417 Figure 6 b, c and d, each group showed a different pattern of response to increasing challenging
418 environmental conditions. In the first group (red) the EBV for DFI decreased as p increased,
419 while the opposite occurred with the third group (green). Within each of these two groups, there
420 were also significant differences in environmental sensibility (slope). Animals with the steepest
421 slopes are more sensible to environmental challenges, consequently less resilient. The second
422 group (blue) gathers those animals that show an intermediate response in terms of the change
423 of EBV according to the value of p . In this group, we can find animals with a positive or
424 negative slope (or even close to zero) but changes in terms of EBV are within -1 and +1 genetic
425 standard deviation. In other words, we can say that the second group gathers those animals less
426 environmentally sensitive (with a less steep slope compared to the other groups). However, due
427 to genetic correlation, selection (if it existed for increased DFI) would shift the distribution to
428 the left. On the contrary, hypothetical selection for decreased DFI would shift the distribution
429 to the right.

430 In Figure 6, we can also see that there is a reordering of genotype ranks and variation in EBV
431 of the animals along the environmental gradient (given by the probability of occurrence of an
432 environmental challenge). This, combined to the results shown in Figure 5 with low genetic
433 correlations among extreme environmental conditions, illustrates the existence of GxE
434 interaction [27].

435 **Discussion**

436

437 *Finite mixture models and estimation of the probability of occurrence of an unrecorded* 438 *environmental challenge for each day*

439

440 Previous studies, based on artificially introduced disturbances (e.g. [1, 5, 6]), showed that there
441 is increased variability in presence of environmental challenges. In this study, we presented a
442 simple and practical approach to estimate the probability that at a given date there was an
443 unrecorded environmental challenge. This is a data-driven approach, as estimations are based
444 only on phenotypic data with no need of extra information as for example climatic information.
445 Compared to other methods, in our approach there is no need of an initial step to estimate an
446 observed or a target curve (with all the parameters that this implies), and the deviations from it
447 to detect the occurrence of environmental challenges. Furthermore, the approach presented in
448 this study can be employed for different datasets coming from different species and with records
449 from different kind of traits as it only focuses on daily (or other time frame) variability, without
450 the need to assume any kind of curve or function for the trait or traits analyzed. Consequently,
451 the method is widely applicable. However, the method requires frequent (daily or similar) data
452 and a homogeneity of animals within groups – for instance, lambs and adults, if they existed,
453 should be analyzed separately.

454

455 We illustrated the data analysis and modeling procedure proposed using a dataset with DFI
456 records from Romane lambs coming from different years. Results indicate that this approach is
457 promising and seems viable to identify unrecorded environmental challenges events, useful
458 when selecting resilient animals and only productive data are available. Although illustrated
459 here using an ovine data set with DFI records, the proposed approach is generalizable to a wide
460 variety of phenotypic records from different species and, given its simplicity, is useful when
461 dealing with large quantities of data coming, for example, from high frequency recording

462 systems such as automated monitoring technology. To our knowledge there are no similar
463 proposals in the literature.

464

465 *Genetic Analysis*

466

467 Detection of environmental challenges affecting the entire population (or contemporary group)
468 can provide a unique opportunity to select resilient animals (or less environmentally sensible)
469 to those events as comparable individuals are exposed to the same environmental conditions.
470 In this study, we evaluated genetic determinism of resilience to these events using the
471 probabilities of occurrence of an environmental challenge as an environmental descriptor in
472 reaction norm animal model. We were able to estimate breeding values for level and
473 environmental sensitivity of DFI for each animal and our results indicate that there is genetic
474 variation in environmental sensitivity. This kind of analysis enables to identify animals that
475 combine both, high production potential with resilience to environmental challenges.

476 Animal breeding practices have become part of the debate since it became recognized that
477 animals selected for high production efficiency are more at risk for behavioral, physiological
478 and immunological problems and are generally less resilient [28, 29, 30]. Consequently, it is
479 important to include resilience or robustness within the breeding goals, however, resilience is
480 not (yet) included in breeding goals of livestock [2].

481 As discussed by Knap [3], one feasible way of breeding for improved animal robustness (or
482 resilience) is estimating breeding values for the environmental sensitivity of the genetic
483 potential for performance through the use of reaction norm analysis. Berghof et al. [2] proposed
484 using the slope of the reaction norm as a resilience indicator. These authors claim that it
485 indicates resilience toward a macro-environmental disturbances (those stressors affecting the
486 whole population, e.g. temperature). In this spirit, we proposed a method to identify

487 environmental challenges and to estimate their probability of occurrence. In this way, we
488 introduced an alternative of an environmental descriptor that takes into account unobserved
489 macro-environmental disturbances to which animals could have been exposed.

490 In this study we obtained a negative genetic correlation between the level of DFI and sensitivity
491 to inferred environmental challenge, showing that a hypothetical selection for increased DFI in
492 non-stressed environments would result in animals that are suboptimal for DFI in stressed
493 environments. On the opposite scenario, a hypothetical selection for decreased DFI it would
494 result in animals with increased DFI in stressful conditions. In both cases, slopes will become
495 steeper (negative or positive, respectively), showing an increase in environmental sensitivity.
496 Negative correlations between level and slope result from resource allocation patterns described
497 by Beilharz et al. [31]. Resource demanding physiological processes show trade-offs resulting
498 from limits in resource availability. In this way, animals that are genetically driven to produce
499 at high levels will probably reallocate resources away from processes related to resilience. A
500 reordering of individual ranks was observed along the environmental gradient as well as a low
501 genetic correlation among extreme environmental conditions. Animals that were good (top of
502 the rank) at $p = 0$ (no challenge) tend to be poor (bottom of the rank) at $p = 1$ (challenge). These
503 confirmed the existence of GxE interaction showing that the best genotype in one
504 environmental condition is not the best in another one [32]. Knowing of the existence of GxE
505 interaction is important in terms of selection decisions.

506 Friggens et al. [4] proposed a categorization of animals into generalists and specialists based
507 on the slope of the individual random regression. Generalists are those animals with a slope
508 relatively close to zero, with a constant performance across different environmental conditions.
509 On the other hand, specialist animals are those with steep slopes (both positive or negative),
510 showing a significantly better performance in extreme environmental conditions (either
511 challenging or non-challenging). However, it is difficult to directly select for generalist animals

512 as this is an intermediate optimum. A possibility would be to select based, not on the reaction
513 norm model (which may indicate the possible existence of resource allocation conflicts), but on
514 the genetic basis of variation itself [33].

515 Previous studies address the issue of resilience from different approaches. For example, some
516 of them analyze the genetic potential of the variance of deviations as an indicator for resilience
517 in dairy milk yield and DFI in pigs [9, 34, 35]. Berghof et al. [8] proposed skewness and
518 autocorrelation of body weight deviations in layer chickens. In this study we proposed an
519 alternative approach and implemented it on an ovine population. As far as we know, little
520 research has been done in small ruminants regarding this matter, usually related to the lack of
521 high frequency records, key to work on resilience. However, resilience in small ruminants is
522 important as they are commonly exposed to heterogeneous and changeful conditions with little
523 control of environmental factors compared to other livestock species, in which production
524 systems are more controlled such as monogastrics. Given these conditions, it is necessary to
525 select animals capable of maintaining their production performance (or modifying it as less as
526 possible) under this heterogeneous environment. This is the reason why resilience to changing
527 environmental factors is of interest when selecting individuals.

528
529

530 **Conclusions**

531
532 Nowadays high frequent data is becoming increasingly available, related to the availability of
533 high frequency recording systems such as automated monitoring technology. The method
534 proposed in this study consists in, first, inferring the existence of highly variable days *via*
535 mixture models applied to frequent phenotypic records and second, using the inferred
536 probabilities of a mixture in a norm reaction model. The approach is simple and practical and
537 can be widely used in different species and traits. This method enables the estimation of the

538 probability of occurrence of an environmental challenge for each day, and this variable proved
539 to be informative and useful to include in genetic analyses as an environmental descriptor to
540 select resilient animals.

541 Here we estimated breeding values for environmental sensitivity of the genetic potential for
542 DFI through the use of reaction norm analysis. The level and the slope showed to be negatively
543 correlated, showing that a hypothetical selection for increased DFI may not be optimal
544 depending on the presence or no of stress. A reordering of individual ranks was observed along
545 the environmental gradient as well as low genetic correlations among extreme environmental
546 conditions. These confirmed the existence of GxE interaction, showing that the best genotype
547 in one environmental condition is not the best in another one.

548

549 **Declarations**

550 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

551 The present study was carried out in agreement with the French National Regulations for
552 humane care and use of animals for research purposes (Décret 2013/118). Animals were bred
553 at the experimental INRAE Farm (La Sapinière, Osmoy, France) which has the experimental
554 approval C18-174-01.

555

556 **Consent for publication**

557 Not applicable.

558

559 **Availability of data and materials**

560 The datasets analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on
561 reasonable request.

562

563 Competing interests

564 The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

565

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569

570 Authors' contributions

571 AL and CAGB conceived the study. CAGB conducted the analyses and wrote the first draft of
572 the manuscript. CME, FT, DM and JLW provided and prepared the ovine dataset. CAGB, CME,
573 FT and AL discussed the results, made suggestions and corrections to refine the manuscript.
574 All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

575

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582

583

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